

SPACE VARIABLES SEPARATION AND PGD MODEL REDUCTION METHOD TO SOLVE ELASTICITY PROBLEMS ON LAMINATED PLATES AND SHELLS

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1 Introduction

Laminated composite parts are more and more used in the industry. Indeed, forming such parts has been practiced for a while now, and the knowledge around processes is now mature. On the other side, the size of manufactured parts is increasing, from ones to tens of meters. These large parts are also more and more used for primary structure of complex systems, leading to thick parts consisting of a great number of plies. Large thickness implies higher thermal effects during forming processes and potentially leads to higher residual stresses and deformations. Due to the large size of both parts and tools, the experimental trial and error correction of the tool in order to obtain an admissible part is not affordable anymore. This, combined with the requirement of rapid design, leads to the massive use of predictive numerical tools in order to avoid experimental adjustment and get a part satisfying the geometrical tolerance on the first attempt.

In order to predict residual stresses and residual deformation of the manufactured part, the suitable physics has to be included in the numerical model. In the case of composite parts with thermosetting matrix, chemical reactions and thermo-mechanical behavior have to be simulated during the forming process to predict the geometry and the stresses in the considered part. Even if the litterature is very rich in the domain of plate and shells theories for elastic problems [3, 5, 9, 8, 7, 4], the resolution of such a problem seems hard to be included in a multi-physic shell formulation. Thus a 3D approach is preferred.

The main idea here is to solve the 3D formulation combined with a model reduction technique to main-

tain reasonable computational costs. This model reduction method is based on the Proper Generalized Decomposition using an in-plane/out-of-plane representation of the quantities.

In the present work, we recall the method proposed for plates [2] and extend it to shells.

2 Resolution of the 3D elasticity on plate geometry

2.1 Introduction of the PGD

Let us consider a linear elasticity problem defined on a domain Ω (see figure 1), where Ω is the considered plate-like domain, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the strain tensor, \mathbf{f}_d is the body force, and \mathbf{F}_d is the surface force applied on the part $\partial_2\Omega$ of the boundary of the domain Ω , and $\partial_1\Omega$ the part of the boundary submitted to a prescribed displacement.

The mechanical problem consists in finding the solution vector field \mathbf{u}_N on Ω , satisfying the virtual work principle:

$$\begin{aligned} \iiint_{\Omega} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}^*) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u})) d\Omega \\ = \iiint_{\Omega} (\mathbf{u}^* \cdot \mathbf{f}_d) d\Omega + \iint_{\partial_2\Omega} (\mathbf{u}^* \cdot \mathbf{F}_d) d\Gamma. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The use of the Proper Generalized Decomposition in plate geometries using an in-plane/out-of-plane variables separation has been detailed in [2]. The main idea is to describe all quantities of the model using a

Figure 1: Considered domain Ω

separated representation as follows:

$$F(x, y, z) \approx \sum_{i=1}^N F_{xy}^i(x, y) \cdot F_z^i(z). \quad (2)$$

According to this formalism, the unknown displacement field is expressed as a sum of products of functions of the in-plane coordinates times a function of the out-of-plane coordinate:

$$\mathbf{u}_N(x, y, z) = \sum_{i=1}^N \begin{pmatrix} u_{xy}^i(x, y) \cdot u_z^i(z) \\ v_{xy}^i(x, y) \cdot v_z^i(z) \\ w_{xy}^i(x, y) \cdot w_z^i(z) \end{pmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{U}_{xy}^i \circ \mathbf{U}_z^i \quad (3)$$

The resolution scheme is the following: assuming \mathbf{u}_N is known, we look for an enriched solution \mathbf{u}_{N+1} involving an additional term in the separated representation [1]:

$$\mathbf{u}_{N+1}(x, y, z) = \mathbf{u}_N + \begin{pmatrix} R_u(x, y) \cdot S_u(z) \\ R_v(x, y) \cdot S_v(z) \\ R_w(x, y) \cdot S_w(z) \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{u}_N + \mathbf{R} \circ \mathbf{S}. \quad (4)$$

The non-linear problem in \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{S} is then solved using a fixed-point algorithm and upon convergence, the newly computed enrichment is added to the solution. We keep on computing new modes until the solution is accurate enough according to a prescribed precision. The enrichment algorithm used to solve the 3D problem is shown in Figure 2.

The solution is initialized with a set of terms satisfying the Dirichlet boundary condition. Further enrichments will therefore be zero on $\partial_1 \Omega$. We assume here that the edge $\partial_1 \Omega$ writes:

$$\partial_1 \Omega = \partial_1 \Omega_{xy} \otimes \partial_1 \Omega_z, \quad (5)$$

where $\partial_1 \Omega_{xy}$ is a sub-domain of the 2D x and y coordinate domain, and $\partial_1 \Omega_z$ is a sub-domain of the 1D z coordinate domain.

Figure 2: General algorithm used to solve the problem

2.2 Resolution of the \mathbf{R} sub-problems

The alternate solution of the \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{S} problems in the fixed point strategy implies an initial guess for the first solution of the \mathbf{R} problem. For the next steps of the \mathbf{R} problem in the fixed point, the previously computed \mathbf{S} function is available. In this work, we consider a random value for each degrees of freedom of the \mathbf{S} function.

Considering the \mathbf{S} function known, the appropriate test function to solve the \mathbf{R} problem is :

$$\mathbf{u}^*(x, y, z) = \mathbf{R}^* \circ \mathbf{S} \quad (6)$$

According to the chosen separated representation, the strain writes:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{R} \circ \mathbf{S}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \begin{pmatrix} R_{u,x} \cdot S_u \\ R_{v,y} \cdot S_v \\ R_w \cdot S_{w,z} \\ R_{w,y} \cdot S_w + R_v \cdot S_{v,z} \\ R_{w,x} \cdot S_w + R_u \cdot S_{u,z} \\ R_{v,x} \cdot S_v + R_{u,y} \cdot S_u \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Then, substituting all terms in the expression of the

$$\begin{aligned} & \iiint_{\Omega} \begin{pmatrix} R_{u,x}^* \cdot S_u \\ R_{v,y}^* \cdot S_v \\ R_w^* \cdot S_{w,z} \\ R_{w,y}^* \cdot S_w + R_v^* \cdot S_{v,z} \\ R_{w,x}^* \cdot S_w + R_u^* \cdot S_{u,z} \\ R_{v,x}^* \cdot S_v + R_{u,y}^* \cdot S_u \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} K_{11}K_{12}K_{13} & 0 & 0 & K_{16} \\ K_{12}K_{22}K_{23} & 0 & 0 & K_{26} \\ K_{13}K_{23}K_{33} & 0 & 0 & K_{36} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & K_{44}K_{45} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & K_{45}K_{55} & 0 \\ K_{16}K_{26}K_{36} & 0 & 0 & K_{66} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} R_{u,x} \cdot S_u \\ R_{v,y} \cdot S_v \\ R_w \cdot S_{w,z} \\ R_{w,y} \cdot S_w + R_v \cdot S_{v,z} \\ R_{w,x} \cdot S_w + R_u \cdot S_{u,z} \\ R_{v,x} \cdot S_v + R_{u,y} \cdot S_u \end{pmatrix} d\Omega \\ & = - \iiint_{\Omega} (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{R}^* \circ \mathbf{S}) : \mathbb{K} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}_N)) d\Omega + \iiint_{\Omega} ((\mathbf{R}^* \circ \mathbf{S}) \cdot \mathbf{f}_d) d\Omega + \iint_{\partial_2 \Omega} ((\mathbf{R}^* \circ \mathbf{S}) \cdot \mathbf{F}_d) d\Gamma \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

virtual work, the \mathbf{R} is rewritten as shown on equation 8.

In order to perform all integrals of the known functions depending of the z coordinate, the matrix-vector product must be expanded. This lead to the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^{41} \lambda_{S_i} \iint_{\Omega_{xy}} (R_{c_i, \alpha_i}^* \cdot R_{d_i, \beta_i}) d\Omega_{xy}}_{\int_{\Omega_z} (S_{c_i, \gamma_i} \cdot K_{m_i n_i}(z) \cdot S_{d_i, \delta_i}) d\Omega_z} \\ & = - \sum_{i=1}^{41N+6} \lambda_i \iint_{\Omega_{xy}} (R_{c_i, \alpha_i}^* \cdot W_{xyi, \beta_i}) d\Omega_{xy} \quad (9) \\ & \underbrace{\int_{\Omega_z} (S_{c_i, \gamma_i} \cdot K_{m_i n_i}(z) \cdot W_{z_i, \delta_i}) d\Omega_z} \end{aligned}$$

Where:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{xyi} & \in [u_{xy}^i, v_{xy}^i, w_{xy}^i, f_{d_{uxy}}, f_{d_{vxy}}, f_{d_{wxy}}, F_{d_{uxy}}, F_{d_{vxy}}, F_{d_{wxy}}] \\ W_{zi} & \in [u_z^i, v_z^i, w_z^i, f_{d_{uz}}, f_{d_{vz}}, f_{d_{wz}}, F_{d_{uz}}, F_{d_{vz}}, F_{d_{wz}}] \\ m_i & \in [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6] \\ n_i & \in [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6] \\ c_i & \in [u, v, w] \\ d_i & \in [u, v, w] \\ \alpha_i & \in [\emptyset, x, y] \\ \beta_i & \in [\emptyset, x, y] \\ \gamma_i & \in [\emptyset, z] \\ \delta_i & \in [\emptyset, z]. \end{aligned}$$

This is a 3-component boundary value problem on

Ω_{xy} for which \mathbf{R} is the unknown. The resulting problem is solved using finite element method.

2.3 Resolution of the \mathbf{S} sub-problems

Having computed \mathbf{R} , we consider then the update of \mathbf{S} . The appropriate test function is used:

$$\mathbf{u}^*(x, y, z) = \mathbf{R} \circ \mathbf{S}^* \quad (10)$$

In the same way that described in the previous subsection, the quantities are substituted in the expression of the virtual work by their respective separated representations, and lead to solve the 3-component unknown \mathbf{S} 1D problem using the finite element method.

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=1}^{41} \lambda_{R_i} \int_{\Omega_z} (S_{c_i, \gamma_i} \cdot K_{m_i n_i}(z) \cdot S_{d_i, \delta_i}) d\Omega_z \\ & \underbrace{\iint_{\Omega_{xy}} (R_{c_i, \alpha_i}^* \cdot R_{d_i, \beta_i}) d\Omega_{xy}}_{\int_{\Omega_z} (S_{c_i, \gamma_i} \cdot K_{m_i n_i}(z) \cdot W_{z_i, \delta_i}) d\Omega_z} \\ & = - \sum_{i=1}^{41N+6} \lambda_i \int_{\Omega_z} (S_{c_i, \gamma_i} \cdot K_{m_i n_i}(z) \cdot W_{z_i, \delta_i}) d\Omega_z \\ & \underbrace{\iint_{\Omega_{xy}} (R_{c_i, \alpha_i}^* \cdot W_{xyi, \beta_i}) d\Omega_{xy}} \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

2.4 Fixed-point convergence check

The alternate solution of the problems in \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{S} keep running until the following stagnation criterion used is met. If we call \mathbf{R}^i and \mathbf{S}^i the functions computed on the i^{th} step of the fixed point, then the convergence is considered reached when:

$$\iint_{\Omega} \|\mathbf{R}^i \circ \mathbf{S}^i - \mathbf{R}^{i-1} \circ \mathbf{S}^{i-1}\| d\Omega < \varepsilon_{\text{fixed point}}. \quad (12)$$

Then, the converged mode is included in the solution:

$$\mathbf{u}_{N+1} = \mathbf{u}_N + \mathbf{R}^i \circ \mathbf{S}^i$$

2.5 Global convergence check

The enrichment loop keep on running adding modes to enrich the solution \mathbf{u} . A criterion is then needed to stop the enrichment process when the desired accuracy is reached. The criterion used here is based on the norm of the relative residual of the problem, with respect to the residual of the unenriched one:

$$\frac{-\iint_{\Omega} (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}^*) \cdot \mathbb{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}_{N+1})) d\Omega + \iint_{\Omega} (\mathbf{u}^* \cdot \mathbf{f}_d) d\Omega}{\iint_{\Omega} (\mathbf{u}^* \cdot \mathbf{f}_d) d\Omega} < \varepsilon_{\text{residue}} \quad (13)$$

Others criteria are possible, based for example on error estimators [6].

2.6 Example

Let us consider a composite plate with a hole in the center, submitted to a prescribed displacement on the right side (see Figure 3)

Figure 3: Definition of the problem

The stacking sequence is $[0, 45, -45, 90]_s$. The geometric dimensions are the following: $a = 200 \cdot 10^{-3} m$, $R = 25 \cdot 10^{-3} m$, $e = 1 \cdot 10^{-3} m$. The material properties are typical properties for unidirectional carbon-epoxy plies.

Figure 4 shows the x component of the displacement field on the plate. The considered approach is particularly suited for the 3D modeling of laminates. Indeed, it allows a very refined mesh in the thickness direction without penalizing the computing time, because the associated problem to solve is a 1D problem, whose cost is negligible in comparison of the cost of the resolution of the 2D problem.

Figure 4: Displacement in the traction direction and on the deformed mesh of the considered plate

Figure 5 shows a detail of the edge of the hole, and emphasizes the alternating positive and negative σ_{zz} stress near the edge of the hole. The refinement of the mesh can be again appreciated on this figure.

Figure 5: Detail of the transverse stress on the edge of the hole

This fully 3D solution is computed in only several minutes using an ordinary laptop with only 4Go of

RAM, while, the reconstruction and display of the solution field over the whole domains requires 16Go of memory.

3 Resolution of the 3D elasticity on shell geometry

3.1 Physical space definition

The idea developed here is to solve the 3D elasticity problem on a shell geometry using a similar representation of quantities as previous described for plates.

The quantities will now be expressed by as sums of products of function involving the reference surface's coordinates (ξ, η) and normal direction's coordinate ζ .

The solution vector field \mathbf{u} will be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_N(\xi, \eta, \zeta) &= \sum_{i=1}^N \begin{pmatrix} u_{\xi\eta}^i(\xi, \eta) \cdot u_{\zeta}^i(\zeta) \\ v_{\xi\eta}^i(\xi, \eta) \cdot v_{\zeta}^i(\zeta) \\ w_{\xi\eta}^i(\xi, \eta) \cdot w_{\zeta}^i(\zeta) \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{u}_{\xi\eta}^i(\xi, \eta) \circ \mathbf{u}_{\zeta}^i(\zeta). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The application $\mathbf{x}_P(\xi, \eta)$ gives the position of the reference surface function of the parametric coordinates ξ and η (see figure 6):

$$\mathbf{x}_P(\xi, \eta) = \begin{pmatrix} X_P(\xi, \eta) \\ Y_P(\xi, \eta) \\ Z_P(\xi, \eta) \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

The tangent vectors to the reference surface at P point can be defined:

$$\mathbf{a}_1 = \mathbf{x}_{P,\xi}(\xi, \eta) \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_2 = \mathbf{x}_{P,\eta}(\xi, \eta) \quad (17)$$

The local normal direction \mathbf{n} is computed as follows:

$$\mathbf{n} = \begin{pmatrix} n_x \\ n_y \\ n_z \end{pmatrix} = \frac{\mathbf{a}_1 \wedge \mathbf{a}_2}{\|\mathbf{a}_1 \wedge \mathbf{a}_2\|} \quad (18)$$

Finally, a point M in the bulk of the shell geometry is defined by its parametric coordinates:

$$\mathbf{x}_M(\xi, \eta) = \mathbf{x}_P(\xi, \eta) + \zeta \mathbf{n}(\xi, \eta) \quad (19)$$

Figure 6: Application from parametric space to physical space

3.2 Resolution of the problem

In order to solve the 3D problem on the shell geometry using the method described in section 2, all quantities must have an adapted separated representation. Then, once substituted in the expression of the virtual work, the algorithm described in Figure 2 can be applied again to solve the problem.

The enrichment of the solution writes:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_{N+1}(\xi, \eta, \zeta) &= \mathbf{u}_N + \begin{pmatrix} R_u(\xi, \eta) \cdot S_u(\zeta) \\ R_v(\xi, \eta) \cdot S_v(\zeta) \\ R_w(\xi, \eta) \cdot S_w(\zeta) \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \mathbf{u}_N + \mathbf{R} \circ \mathbf{S} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Then, the resolution method is exactly the same as the one previously presented.

However the expression of the gradient of the displacement field, the material coefficients and the differential element for volume and surface, which are trivial for a Cartesian coordinate system, are more complex in the case of a shell geometry.

3.3 Expression of the strain

According to the expression of the position of a point M , the gradient of the displacement can be written as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \mathbf{x}}. \quad (21)$$

Where:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial \xi} = \sum_{i=1}^N \begin{pmatrix} u_{\xi\eta,\xi}^i \cdot u_{\zeta}^i & u_{\xi\eta,\eta}^i \cdot u_{\zeta}^i & u_{\xi\eta}^i \cdot u_{\zeta,\zeta}^i \\ v_{\xi\eta,\xi}^i \cdot v_{\zeta}^i & v_{\xi\eta,\eta}^i \cdot v_{\zeta}^i & v_{\xi\eta}^i \cdot v_{\zeta,\zeta}^i \\ w_{\xi\eta,\xi}^i \cdot w_{\zeta}^i & w_{\xi\eta,\eta}^i \cdot w_{\zeta}^i & w_{\xi\eta}^i \cdot w_{\zeta,\zeta}^i \end{pmatrix}, \quad (22)$$

and:

$$\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \mathbf{x}} = \begin{pmatrix} X_{P,\xi} + \zeta n_{x,\xi} & X_{P,\eta} + \zeta n_{x,\eta} & n_x \\ Y_{P,\xi} + \zeta n_{y,\xi} & Y_{P,\eta} + \zeta n_{y,\eta} & n_y \\ Z_{P,\xi} + \zeta n_{z,\xi} & Z_{P,\eta} + \zeta n_{z,\eta} & n_z \end{pmatrix}^{-1}. \quad (23)$$

All components of the second order tensor $\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \xi}$ are evaluated on the whole domain Ω , the inverse $\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \mathbf{x}}$ is then computed. Finally, a singular values decomposition is performed on each component of $\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \mathbf{x}}$ in order to get a separated representation compatible with the chosen decomposition.

The expression of the strain can then be developed by substituting the quantities by their separated representation in the expression:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \mathbf{x}} + \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \mathbf{x}}^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial \xi} \right). \quad (24)$$

3.4 Material properties

The material properties must be expressed in the same basis as all other quantities. For a laminate composite material coefficients are easy to define in a local orthonormal basis $(\mathbf{t}_1, \mathbf{t}_2, \mathbf{t}_3 \equiv \mathbf{n})$ (see figure 7), where \mathbf{t}_1 and \mathbf{t}_2 are arbitrary chosen unit tangent vectors to the reference surface.

Figure 7: Representation of local and global basis: local basis: $(\mathbf{t}_1, \mathbf{t}_2, \mathbf{t}_3)$, global basis: $(\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y, \mathbf{e}_z)$

Then, the elasticity tensor is expressed in the global basis as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{K}(\xi, \eta, \zeta) &= \left(\sum_{i=1}^p \mathbb{K}^P(\xi, \eta) \cdot \delta^P(\zeta) \right)_{(\mathbf{t}_1, \mathbf{t}_2, \mathbf{t}_3)} \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=1}^p \left(\overline{\mathbf{Q}}^T(\xi, \eta) \mathbb{K}^P(\xi, \eta) \overline{\mathbf{Q}}(\xi, \eta) \right) \cdot \delta^P(\zeta) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Where $\mathbb{K}^P(\xi, \eta)$ is the elasticity tensor for plies of orientation θ^P , and $\overline{\mathbf{Q}}(\xi, \eta)$ transformation matrix from $(\mathbf{t}_1, \mathbf{t}_2, \mathbf{t}_3)$ to $(\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y, \mathbf{e}_z)$. $\delta^P(\zeta)$ equals to 1 in plies of orientation θ^P , and 0 otherwise.

3.5 Differential elements

In order to integrate properly all quantities in the curvilinear space, the volume differential element is necessary for volume integrals, and the surface differential element for surfaces integrals. Those differential elements are classically used in differential geometry.

The elementary surface element dA_ζ writes:

$$dA_\zeta = \| \mathbf{a}_{1\zeta} \wedge \mathbf{a}_{2\zeta} \| d\xi d\eta = \sqrt{a_\zeta} d\xi d\eta, \quad (26)$$

where:

$$\sqrt{a_\zeta} = \sqrt{\mathbf{a}}(1 - 2H\zeta + K\zeta^2), \quad (27)$$

where H and K are respectively the mean and the Gaussian curvature. The volume element $d\Omega$ writes:

$$d\Omega = (\mathbf{a}_{1\zeta} d\xi \wedge \mathbf{a}_{2\zeta} d\eta) \cdot \mathbf{n} d\zeta = dA_\zeta d\zeta. \quad (28)$$

Using equation 27, we finally obtain:

$$d\Omega = \sqrt{\mathbf{a}}(1 - 2H\zeta + K\zeta^2) d\xi d\eta d\zeta. \quad (29)$$

3.6 Validation case

Let us consider the problem illustrated in Figure 8 of an infinitely long pipe submitted to an inner unit pressure. The inner radius is such $a = 2mm$ and the external radius is $b = 3mm$.

Figure 8: Representation of a section of the considered problem

	N_ξ	N_η	N_ζ
MESH 1	8	2	2
MESH 2	16	2	4
MESH 3	32	2	8

Table 1: Number of elements for the 3 meshes used to solve the problem

The analytic solution of the continuum mechanics problem writes:

$$u_r(r) = \frac{1 + \nu}{E(b^2 - a^2)} \left[(1 - 2\nu)(a^2 P_i r) + \frac{a^2 b^2 P_i}{r} \right]. \quad (30)$$

Because of the plane strain state of the problem, an arbitrary length of the cylinder can be considered with appropriate boundary conditions for the numerical resolution of the problem.

The cylindrical reference surface is expressed as follows:

$$\begin{cases} X = \frac{R_{mean}}{2\pi} \sin\left(\frac{\xi}{R_{mean}}\right) \\ Y = \eta \\ Z = \frac{R_{mean}}{2\pi} \cos\left(\frac{\xi}{R_{mean}}\right) \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

The domain in the thickness direction is such that $\zeta \in [-0.5; 0.5]$.

The numerical solution is computed using both 3D finite element method and PGD based 2D/1D separated representation method. Several meshes with successive refinements (see table 1) are used in order to check the convergence. The results are summarized on figure 9.

We observe that the theoretical displacement is quickly reached with both numerical method when refining the meshes. However, because the PGD based method uses the differential geometry tools, keeping the knowledge of the curvatures, the solution is better than the 3D FEM solution with equivalent discretization.

3.7 Complex example

The accuracy of the presented method was illustrated in the previous section. Let us consider now a more challenging case.

The considered geometry is a cylindrical part with stiffeners and oblong holes (see Figure 10) on which we solve the 3D elasticity. The considered loading here is an internal unit pressure.

Figure 9: Radial displacement along a radius for the 3 different meshes, and for the analytical solution

Figure 10: Representation of the 3D geometry

The 3D reconstructed solution involves 70 million of hexaedral trilinear elements, and 300 million degrees of freedom. The parametric mesh for the 2D problem contains 175 000 bilinear quadrangular elements, and the parametric mesh for the thickness direction is composed of 400 1D linear elements. The solution displacement field is presented Figure 11.

4 Conclusion

The method presented here allow to perform 3D elastic simulations on plates and shells geometries with

Figure 11: Magnitude of the solution displacement field

moderate computational cost. Indeed, because only 2D and 1D problems are ever solved, the characteristic cost for the resolution of the 3D problem on a plate or shell geometry scales like a 2D computational cost. The resolution of each 1D problems involving the thickness direction can be neglected compared to the 2D problem in terms of cost.

Therefore, a very fine representation of the thickness direction is affordable and the method provides very rich solution across the thickness. This is particularly suited for laminates and all multilayered materials.

The compact representation of all quantities using products of 2D and 1D functions leads to computational and storage efficiency of the presented method.

Moreover, the accuracy of the solution field is controlled, and in most cases, a very limited number of modes is necessary to describe the 3D displacement field.

Finally, this method open new perspectives in the resolution of elastic problems defined on plate and shell geometries, and very fine description of the solution can be reached with limited computational costs.

References

[1] A Ammar, B Mokdad, F Chinesta, and R Keunings. A new family of solvers for some classes of multidimensional partial differential equations

encountered in kinetic theory modelling of complex fluids - Part II: Transient simulation using space-time separated representations. *Journal Of Non-Newtonian Fluid Mechanics*, 144(2-3):98–121, 2007.

- [2] B Bognet, A Leygue, F Chinesta, A Poitou, and F Bordeu. Advanced Simulation of Models Defined in Plate Geometries: 3D Solutions with 2D Computational Complexity. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 201-204:1–12, 2012.
- [3] E Carrera. Theories and finite elements for multilayered, anisotropic, composite plates and shells. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, 9(2):87–140, June 2002.
- [4] Erasmo Carrera. Historical review of Zig-Zag theories for multilayered plates and shells. *Applied Mechanics Reviews*, 56(3):287, 2003.
- [5] Erasmo Carrera. Theories and Finite Elements for Multilayered Plates and Shells:A Unified compact formulation with numerical assessment and benchmarking. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, 10(3):215–296, September 2003.
- [6] Pierre Ladevèze and Ludovic Chamoin. On the verification of model reduction methods based on the proper generalized decomposition. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 200(23-24):2032–2047, June 2011.
- [7] Mohammad S. Qatu. Review of Recent Literature on Static Analyses of Composite Shells: 2000-2010. *Open Journal of Composite Materials*, 02(03):61–86, 2012.
- [8] J. N. Reddy and R. a. Arciniega. Shear Deformation Plate and Shell Theories: From Stavsky to Present. *Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures*, 11(6):535–582, November 2004.
- [9] Erasmo Viola, Francesco Tornabene, and Nicholas Fantuzzi. Static analysis of completely doubly-curved laminated shells and panels using general higher-order shear deformation theories. *Composite Structures*, 101:59–93, July 2013.